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THE LEVEL OF PHYSICAL TRAINING OF ATHLETES

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Abstract. *In this article, functional training determines the results and achievements of athletes at the global level. An important scientific problem in the world of sports is characterized by the study of the dependence of high loads and extreme conditions on the level of physical capabilities of people, the health of the body, and the impact of loads on the body.*

Keywords: *athletics, quick-strength, physical training, research, athletes, recovery.*

INTRODUCTION

To date, the complex relationship of many parameters of bioimpedanceometric, cardiorespiratory, vestibulometric and "quick-power" quality testing methods has not been fully studied. An important condition for effective use of the results obtained by the above research methods is their correct interpretation. This requires deep application of mathematical analysis methods together with determination of high-precision relationships between indicators. There are few researches devoted to this problem both in our country and abroad.

Physiological measures to increase the effectiveness of recovery are currently divided into pedagogical, psychological, medical, and physiological measures that accelerate recovery. While the first 3 measures are well studied and detailed in the literature, the physiological measures are less clear. Of course, they are to a certain extent related to medical and other activities, but they have their own characteristics. The theoretical justification of the physiological measures that accelerate the recovery process is based on the study of the physiological laws of the body's sports activities and functional reserves.

They include monitoring the state of the body's functions, working capacity and fatigue dynamics during training and competition, as well as activation and use of the body's functional reserves to accelerate recovery. The integral indicator of the assessment of the effectiveness of recovery processes is the level of general and special work ability. All physiological measures of recovery can be divided into 2 groups: permanent and periodic. Permanent measures are aimed at preventing negative functional

changes, maintaining and increasing non-specific endurance and physiological reserves of the body, preventing early fatigue and extreme fatigue in athletes. Such measures include the rational organization of training sessions and rest, proper nutrition, provision of additional vitamins, use of general physical exercises that strengthen the body, and optimization of the emotional state. These measures are familiar to many people and there is no need to describe them in detail.

Periodic measures, as necessary, are focused on using the reserve capabilities of the body in order to immediately restore and increase the working capacity of athletes. Such measures include stimulation of biologically active points, breathing of pure oxygen at standard and high 88 atmospheric pressure, training in hypoxia, massage, ultraviolet radiation, heat treatments, as well as the use of biological stimulants and adaptogenic substances unrelated to doping, and others included. Some of these measures have been studied and applied to sports practice, and the use of some of them requires special caution, especially when using pharmacological agents. Firstly, some substances that were not considered doping before are now classified as doping substances, and secondly, their regular intake can lead to the exhaustion of the body's reserves and the occurrence of diseases due to a decrease in non-specific resistance of the body.

Stimulants and adaptogens derived from plants (ginseng, eleutherococcus, Chinese lemon, etc.) are among the most common biologically active substances used to accelerate regeneration processes and increase work capacity. They have a wide range of effects, low toxicity, are used as a tonic and stimulant for the body when performing important tasks, to accelerate adaptation, to increase the general non-specific resistance of the body, and to improve regeneration processes. In conditions where very quick recovery is necessary, drugs with a stimulating effect can be recommended. Such substances quickly eliminate fatigue, accelerate the regeneration of plastic and energetic processes, and increase the ability of the cocktail. They have a positive effect only in case of significant fatigue. Sindocarb, bimethyl, pirocitam, oligofen and actovi can be included among such substances. They restore functional conditions by immediately activating the reserve potentials preserved in the body.

It should be remembered that long-term use of these substances without a break can cause unwanted changes in the body. Therefore, in order to achieve a good result, it is recommended to organize the order of reception correctly, to take an individual approach to determining the amount of the drug according to the description of a person's functional status and sports activity. Controlling the processes of restoration of body functions is a complex task, and its implementation requires specialists and necessary equipment. However, relatively simple methods have also been developed. For example, after waking up in the morning, you can use the method of counting the number of heartbeats without getting up. In this method, if the difference in the number of daily heartbeats does not exceed 2-4, then the load corresponds to the body's capabilities and indicates that the regeneration processes are going well. The second method is orthostatic testing, 89 in which the heart rate is counted while the person is lying down, then slowly standing up, and if the difference is less than 16, recovery is good, 16-18 is satisfactory, and more than 18 is satisfactory. Isa indicates that the recovery is not complete and there is excessive fatigue. Thus, the issue of body regeneration is important in sports and requires the development of new scientifically based measures and tools.

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